

**"REPRODUCTIVE FREEDOM AGAINST PREIMPLANTATION GENETIC
DIAGNOSIS FOR THERAPEUTIC PURPOSES OF THIRD PARTIES IN
MEXICO"****JESÚS DURAN CUJ***Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2344-2824>***CARLOS ROMEO RODRIGUEZ MAZARIEGO***Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6467-6278>**cromeorodmaz87@hotmail.com***LUIS ABRAHAM PAZ MEDINA***Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7047-3773>***MARISOL GONZÁLEZ HERNÁNDEZ***Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1869-607X>***YAZMÍN ISOLDA ÁLVAREZ GARCÍA***Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0587-0406>***ABSTRACT**

This addresses as a topic of interest reproductive freedom against the assisted reproduction technique in its justification as preimplantation genetic diagnosis for therapeutic purposes to third parties, so it executes an analysis of the particular concepts that will be addressed in the discussion, in turn of the subjects involved and the legal precepts that serve as national and international antecedents in the subject of family planning law and How this right to freedom can be contrasted in a line of weighting to other human rights such as health, best interests of the child, identity, among others.

Keywords: Babies medicines, Human rights, Assisted reproduction, Health.

1. INTRODUCTION

This research paper reports the results of an exhaustive documentary exploration to motivate the real and current need for legal regulation in assisted reproduction technique such as in vitro fertilization through Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis for therapeutic purposes for third parties, Although, in our current legislation we can find legal gaps that delimit the exercise of this medical practice, It is this then, a legislative crack that must be considered to attack, correct and promote the objective use of genetic manipulation because currently in our territorial extension of the United Mexican States in some of its states the figure of assisted reproduction in its aspects such as surrogate and surrogate motherhood gives guidelines for the exercise of this assumption as an instrument to correct health problems unrelated to the embryo that has been perfected without To deepen whether the concepts of life, doctrine and conventional and constitutional laws support regulated the legal framework of what is called "minors" (children). The question is, can the law be so elastic and permissible in the face of the concepts of "life" and "best interests of the child"? ¿Do children's human rights in turn apply to unborn children? Why is it important to legislate on the subject of preimplantation genetic diagnosis? And how this technique allows us to analyze the importance of the right to reproductive freedom in the face of the need to be able to bring to life a minor with specific characteristics to save the life of another human being.

2. METHOD.

The qualitative research approach was used, this article is documentary and exploratory because the collection of information was carried out to know the context and current situation of the figure in question, carrying out its study and analysis, establishing new ways of understanding the legal figure under discussion and the relationship it has with other legal phenomena.

3. RESULTS

As time passes we wonder what is the meaning of the word life and where it begins, our cultural memory refers us to the main theories of the origin of life not as a human in matter and form but as a set of cells that after a while evolves giving way to a solid and visible being. But, in the common language we observe with objective and subjective definitions of the word, so when considering a problem of a social nature due to the polarization of the idea of the word itself, we get to have confrontations of opinions forgetting the range of the diversity of positions that may come to exist being each valid, Just emphasizing that for the conformation of the legal sphere it is necessary to take into account the most realistic and current results so that the solution embodied in a norm is suitable in the limitation of the exercise of our freedom.

The above mentioned is a proper and particular perspective as well as general and interpretative but what concerns is the question of focusing the meaning of the concept of life that handles the main dictionaries of the Spanish language.

The Royal Spanish Academy (RAE, 2001) shares the general meaning of this concept of "life" from the Latin *vita* and that the letter mentions "2 f. State of activity of organic beings". For its part, the legal encyclopedia takes up the same previous signifier mentioned by the RAE, but with the following adherent "The manifestation and activity of being (...) Time that elapses from birth to death. Way of living or customs and practices of a person, family or social group. Unity or union of man's body and soul." But we must make a parenthesis between the different substantial meanings, we can find a great diversity of connotations because we would no longer be talking about the meaning itself but the signifier that is assigned according to the context that is going to be applied.

To unravel the question Where does life begin? It is necessary to locate oneself in the corresponding science responsible primarily for the scientific study of the structure of organic beings and their formation, adaptation and development in their natural environment. It is, therefore, that attached to the rigor implied by the development of this article, it is necessary to emphasize that the classification of life will be taken from the biological point of view, leaving aside prejudices with cultural reasons.

3.1 When life begins according to biology

It is important to point out by way of example that throughout our human development we go through stages, stages of life to which a name is given, naming them children, puberts, adolescents, young people, adults, elderly to the human at every moment of his life, but not only do we have these derivatives of the classification of time and age that is counted from when we are born from inside the maternal womb until the first inhalations. postpartum oxygen. Before being interactive matter called babies, we were more than the set of cells and molecules of different compounds that due to the attraction of these cells with the passage of space-time solidify opening the way to the creation of a living organic product with autonomy and independence, with senses and consciousness.

In this period of reproduction we find that the stages are not only after birth, but from the fertilization of two cellulose organisms called spermatozoa product of the human male sex and the recipient an egg produced by the female sex.

In her research, Dr. Rosalinda Cruz de Williams in 2017 in the area of Tegucigalpa, Honduras belonging to the Central American region shares in the most similar way to a research article the reproductive process starting with the first phase of fertilization all in order to understand that beyond the signifiers provided by our context and our sources of consultation it is necessary to manifest clearly that the perspective of the starting point of living beings are methodologically and scientifically observed equating their state of mind that reinforces the categorization of life and exemplifies it as follows:

According to the methodological studies concerning the matter, the birth of life occurs in the period of fertilization, with the primary figure of the zygote. This zygote is the effect of the union of two germ cells or gametes. After the sperm crosses the membrane of the egg, the pronuclei fuse and a potential human toti cell appears, which is the zygote, the first embryonic cell, which develops to produce the so-called blastocyst, or embryo of a few days. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 2)

The embryo grows and its cells multiply through biological development in a continuous and gradual manner. Although it is dependent on the mother, at the same time it is autonomous. Certain morphological elements appear, which configure their phenotype. The whole process is within a vital unit, marked by the genetic program that identifies him as a human being. It is his genetic code, so unique and personal that it makes him different from any other human being. In other words: the embryo changes morphologically, but its substantial identity does not change, it remains the same human being, unique and unrepeatable. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 2)

The genome is in each and every cell of the embryo. The growth, development and functional differentiation of its cells depend on the genome to form tissues, organs and systems. All this arises from the zygote, the first potential totipotent cell, which carries within itself the instructions to form a complete human being. The zygote is already a human life, constituted at first by a single cell that later undergoes successive divisions, giving way to the blastocyst, morula, gastrula, etc. Therefore, it cannot be said that these cellular organizations constitute a "cellular conglomerate", since they have unity of organization and life. They have the same and unique identity. Its development corresponds to the process of a living being, belonging to the human species, supported by the crossing of the genes of its parents that give it a perfect and unique identity. Identity that is numerically distinct from the paternal-maternal identity (it is another living being of the same species). In this new human being there is no organizational, embryonic or fetal phase that is not human. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 3)

In addition to genetic mechanisms, there are a number of biochemical mechanisms that regulate the process of embryo evolution. Their cells lose their potential totipotent character (ability to generate "all" cell types), but they have the ability to generate different cell types. This process is not arbitrary, but is genetically regulated; And so appear the muscle, nerve, epithelial cells, each with its own functionality. This ability to differentiate into functional cells tells us again that from its early stages, the embryo is a living being of human nature. This is already the case when the biochemical dialogue between the embryo and the mother is established, which is a mechanism to control that the embryo is directed and puts in contact with the uterine mucosa of the mother, where nesting will occur. From nesting, the same embryo obtains from the mother its food, which until then came from the cytoplasm of the egg. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 3)

From nesting or implantation, the placenta will develop in the mother's womb for the exchange of oxygen and nutrients. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 3)

These are some of the biological arguments to be able to affirm that the being resulting from the union of the egg with the sperm is a living and human being. Therefore, this developing human being has the same dignity and deserves the same respect as an adult human being. Your human being does not come as a result of that development, but is a necessary and precondition for that development. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 3)

Therefore, at the same time that this biological development occurs, we cannot forget that we are facing a subject, a you, who speaks to us from the genetic, molecular, hormonal and vital code. This living being establishes with its environment the dialogue proper to life, emitting unequivocal signals that there is life organizing, with a development initiated from the first moment (the zygote),

and until its natural death. (de Williams, R. C. 2017, p. 4) de Williams, R. C. (n.d.). The right to life in article 6 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. Googleusercontent.com. Retrieved June 17, 2022, from https://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:Mkc57POd_uAJ:https://www.ohchr.org/Documents/HRBodies/CCPR/GCArticle6/Dra.RosalindaCruzdeWilliams.docx+&cd=1&hl=es-419&ct=clnk&gl=mx

I am... a human being. My embryonic beginning. (n/d). Barbastroporlvida. Retrieved June 17, 2022, from <https://barbastroporlvida.blogia.com/2012/030901-yo-soy-...un-ser-humano.-mi-comienzo-embrionario..php>

3.2 What is the assisted reproduction technique?

Embryocenter, 2016. Assisted Reproduction Techniques (ART) for the treatment of sterility are characterized by the application of a series of controlled manipulation procedures of gametes (eggs and sperm) and / or embryos in highly specialized laboratories, necessary to carry out intrauterine insemination (IUI) and in vitro fertilization (IVF). Other techniques such as the preservation of frozen or vitrified embryos (cryopreservation of embryos) and preimplantation genetic diagnosis have emerged as a result of the development of IVF.

The existence of sterility will not always need ART to be the first option to consider, as there are times when its cause is a mild disorder that can be solved with more conventional treatments or with behaviors based on enhancing health and reproductive habits. If these alternatives do not achieve the expected result, that is when the useful alternative of resorting to ART arises.

What are Assisted Reproduction Techniques. (2016, November 2). Embryocenter - Fertility Clinic in Seville; Embryocenter. Assisted reproduction clinic. <https://embryocenter.es/que-son-tecnicas-reproduccion-asistida/>

3.3 In vitro insemination

It is called artificial insemination to the methodology of implantation of sperm previously selected in laboratories with the purpose of increasing the probability of fertilization of the egg and in turn increase the possibility of pregnancy stimulating through hormonal treatments to the ovaries thus controlling ovulation by succeeding when it is suitable for artificial insemination. (n/d). Assisted Reproduction. 2022)

What is artificial insemination and what does it consist of? (n/d). Assisted Reproduction. Retrieved June 18, 2022, from <https://www.quironsalud.es/reproduccionasistida/es/tratamientos-tecnicas-servicios/inseminacion-artificial>

3.4 Preimplantation genetic diagnosis

It consists of a diagnostic technique to check the "genetic health" of a living embryo, in vitro, before deciding either its transfer to the mother's uterus or its discarding for a procreative purpose, in order to prevent the birth of children with serious hereditary diseases. But the truth is that this technique is not presented today only as an instrument to combat the transmission of hereditary pathologies, but, in addition, around it begins to open an extraordinary range of options and possibilities for human

beings, which feeds in some fantasies such as the perfect baby, the improvement of the race, the optimization of the body, etc. Logically, behind the above is hovering the ghost of classical eugenics and here, therefore, is one of the most obvious dangers presented by the uncontrolled development of PGD. However, at the same time that dark and worrying areas are glimpsed, it is also appreciated that PGD can be configured as a valuable element for the development of reproductive freedom of those parents who wish to guarantee the best possible health conditions for their children. There is talk then of the emergence of a new concept of responsible parenthood that uses genetic information to decide their reproductive choices and a new type of eugenics, the so-called "neo-eugenics", which presents important nuances that clearly differentiate it from classical eugenics (essentially the fact that it has its origin in the reproductive freedom of individuals or couples, and not in state policies as before). Journal of the School of Legal Medicine September 2006 Bioethical and legal aspects of preimplantation genetic diagnosis (GPD) 16 Abellán F. In the end, one of the basic problems will be where we ethically and legally place the limit of the satisfaction of the wishes of parents and the barriers to protecting the genetic identity of future generations, but also to what extent, if any, society should intervene, through the State. to limit reproductive freedom in this field. (Abellán, F. 2006)

Abellán, F. (April 5, 2006). Bioethical and legal aspects of preimplantation genetic diagnosis (GPD) [to the Faculty of Medicine of the Complutense University].

3.5 Therapeutic effects on third parties

Although the initial purpose of PGD was to prevent the transmission of hereditary diseases linked to sex, today it has developed a spectacular range of possibilities that expand not only the reproductive freedom of parents.

From this point of view, it has been argued that PGD can be configured as a valuable element for the development of reproductive freedom of those parents who wish to guarantee the best possible health conditions for their children (ABELLÁN, F., op. cit., p. 2).

but therapeutic solutions for certain diseases, However, it has been argued that strict sensu PGD does not operate as a therapeutic solution for the pathologies suffered by the embryo. Indeed, the technique pursues the molecular visualization of certain genetic traits directly or indirectly linked to a disease. If the result of the analysis reveals the existence of a chromosomal abnormality, the medical indication will always be non-implantation. From this point of view, PGD proposes a new meaning of therapy more focused on the purposes - avoid pregnancy and subsequent birth of a sick child - than on the means, that is, cure the sick child in its early stages of development (VIVANCO SIERRALTA, L., Pre-implantation genetic diagnosis (PGD). Scientific, anthropological, philosophical, bioethical and biolegal aspects linked to an emerging reality in Spain, Dykinson, Madrid, 2011, p. 23).

From this point of view, it has been said that PGD constitutes, together with stem cell research, the future of medicine.

Vid. IRIBERRI, A., "Preimplantation diagnosis is the future of medicine", El Mundo, Salud, December 13, 2012, available at the following link:

<http://www.elmundo.es/elmundosalud/2012/12/12/noticias/1355338631.html>.

3.6 Reproductive autonomy, genetic selection of embryos and the search for the "drug baby"

The use or implementation of PGD is a means by which parents take actions for reproductive autonomy and family planning in all the extension of the word, through genetic studies parents can determine and intervene in the offspring they wish to have, this argument based on the fact of currently having scientific and medical advances with greater tools and knowledge resulting in better control and management reproductive of individuals, and as the most important point to achieve personal and family fulfillment by having the possibility of using the relevant procedures and intervening in the characteristics of their offspring as they consider to ensure their interest and best interests of the conceived.

They are called "medicine babies" to, children conceived to be compatible donors to rescue, exemplifying, through a bone marrow transplant, a sibling who suffers from an innate immune pathology.

Undoubtedly, the construction of a child artificially and its selection by means of preimplantation genetic diagnosis (PGD) techniques is the exclusive option to obtain a child with the exact properties to be able to cure another sick child. However, the procedure creates many ethical questions that should be taken into account.

The method is based on ovarian stimulation of the mother to fertilize various eggs and choose compatible embryos among them. Once the quality control is passed, one or two are implanted in the mother and, once the infant is born, the blood is collected from his umbilical cord (UCS) and, after processing, try with it the sick brother. The rest of embryos, which are graphically called "leftovers", are, therefore, discarded or frozen.

In summary, in order to make a healthy baby compatible with his sick brother, several eggs must be obtained from the mother, fertilized in the laboratory, examined one by one and choose the non-carrier and compatible and achieve implantation and obstetric triumph.

3.7 PGD and reproductive freedom

The use of PGD broadens the reproductive autonomy of parents promotes the conscious development of the family nucleus with the aim of procuring a procreative common good. As research brings is through a procedure of in vitro fertilization that in a premeditated way is modified or genetically oriented the product of fertilization with the aim that the product is genetically compatible with the third party that requires treatment, in a few words through this a baby is conceived in order to save his brother, Hence its different nomenclatures "Baby miracle" "Drink medicine" "Lifeguard brother" in this way parents have the ability and possibility to decide on their reproductive health.

Based on this criterion, we have the possibility to ensure that the third interest with constitutional relevance that is implicated in the extensive PGD is the right to reproduction of fathers. In impact, the LTRHA of 2006 has regulated a method that expands the range of reproductive modalities of

fathers because it makes it possible to have a child who is not only independent of a hereditary pathology, but also manages to serve as a donor to a sick brother. Our analysis, therefore, should focus on analyzing the term, motive and content of the right to reproduction of fathers in the Spanish legal system. Such, we will be in a position to draw conclusions about the interaction that exists between PGD and a hypothetical right to have a healthy "savior" child from a third party.

Reproductive rights, therefore, allow individuals to make free and causative choices about the probability of procreating, of regulating fertility and of having the information and means to do so. The right to determine the number of children, spacing and spacing between births is therefore recognized. In the same way, they understand the right to have access to reproductive health services that guarantee safe motherhood, the prevention of unwanted pregnancies and the prevention and procedure of pathologies of the reproductive system.

3.8 Best interests of the child

No current decision about the minor, his interest and implications, can have any other relevance than temporary, necessary and subject to review and updating as he grows and changes – because his interest, what is best for him, also changes--, in which he must participate progressively, in that updating of decisions that affect the minor himself as he evolves with age and has a growing aptitude and need for self-affirmation. Participation, in turn to a variable extent depending on whether they are decisions with a greater or lesser load of rational or emotional and affective elements, depending on the case because their preparation to decide on what requires prior information and reasoning before deciding, is not the same as for what is based on feeling and sensitivity. (Santiago R. C; Hernández D. E. 2019. "The Best Interests of the Child in Mexican Procedural Law")

The achievement of the concept of child as a subject of rights and as a person with specific developmental needs has been progressive; Perhaps our social representation should be reviewed again to reaffirm it, in the light of cognitive psychology, psychoanalysis and integrative transpersonal psychology, whose main contribution to the issue at hand has been the concept of evolutionary development of girls and boys. (Santiago R. C; Hernández D. E. 2019. "The Best Interests of the Child in Mexican Procedural Law")

3.9 Constitutional and conventional legal regulation

Within the Mexican legal system we find the fundamental pillar of the normative body in the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States, which within its conformation contemplates since its establishment a dogmatic and organic part prevailing in the lives of the people who are in national territory, recognizing in favor of the inhabitants of the state the constitutional guarantees, In addition to the rights of both constitutional and conventional sources in matters relating to the free development of family planning, it is pertinent and necessary, which is why a normative support of high hierarchy such as the rights of conventional and constitutional source inevitably refer to the following article and I quote:

"Article 4: Women and men are equal before the law. It will protect the organization and development of the family.

Everyone has the right to decide in a free, responsible and informed manner on the number and spacing of their children." (CPEUM, 1917)

We must understand that this is a social unit, plural and complex, not a simple collection of units, of separate individuals, which we have to defend as such, as individuals; If we are to admit that the family nucleus is a social whole, that it is the cell of every society, that it is a natural whole, that it is a primary whole, it should be regulated as such, as a whole, attending to the preeminent interest of the family nucleus made up of all its resources, we do not have the possibility of facing the interests of each one: of the infant, the girl, the young man, the adolescent, the elderly, the lady, as if they were individualities, we have to reconcile the interests of all to achieve the interest of unity completely; the State is what their families are, the human race is what their States are, we have to start from the term of that base and regulate the family nucleus as the nucleus or cell of society, incorporated by different individuals linked indissolubly, inseparably, only in this way can I understand the family nucleus.

It is for all this that the regulation and protection of the family as a complex unit finds support in the CPEUM and not only because of the complexity itself but through different instruments the rights of individuals of adult age to form a family must be recognized, on the basis of equality and maintaining the principle of non-discrimination. Articles 3, 23 and 26 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, n.d.).

Individuals of adult age, without limitation, have the right to marry and to found a family. They enjoy equal rights for marriage, during marriage and in the event of its dissolution. (Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Art. 16)

Family planning as a human right promoting reproductive autonomy.

Family planning is a Constitutional Human Right in its Art.4^o is why the promotion and awareness favors the knowledge and approach of the population to each time new means to carry it out in a timely manner in Mexico.

The first family idealization programs were aimed at minimizing fertility rates and population growth. At present, the conception of family organization not only conceives it as a human right, it also recognizes in its exercise the probability of entering other rights such as health, education and the enjoyment of a better quality of life.

Under this approach, the Ministry of Health established the Specific Action Program. Family Planning and Contraception. 2013-2018, which has three objectives:

- 1) increase effective access to services and improve the quality of family planning and contraceptive care;
- (2) address the specific needs of the population for family planning and contraception, particularly in socially disadvantaged groups; and
- 3) encourage active and elected parenthood and male responsibility for family planning and contraception.

"This year, the United Nations celebrates 50 years of the Tehran Declaration, in the framework of World Population Day 2018 and proposes nine standards to exercise the human right to family planning:

No discrimination, Availability, Accessibility, Acceptability, Quality, Decision making, Privacy and confidentiality, Participation, Responsibility"

(Secretary of Health, 2018)

The foregoing, according to the support of the Secretary of the Interior, clearly indicates that the family, and the development of it, that decision is fundamentally of those who conform it and plan according to their life plan and full conscience, that is why it denotes and shows the reproductive autonomy of the parents.

The United Nations Population Fund, UNFPA, contributes to expanding access to family planning in developing countries through strategies aimed at ensuring a reliable supply of a wide range of modern contraceptives, strengthening national health systems and promoting gender equality.

UNFPA is fully committed to sustainably supporting countries' efforts to uphold the right of people, especially women, to plan a family.

Traditionally, reproductive sovereignty has been referred to the origin of sexual and reproductive rights since the sixties of the last century. From this vision, it has been configured as a kind of "negative freedom" from the State that should not interfere in questions in relation to procreation and sexuality by remaining protected by the right to privacy. These demands related to birth control, contraception, and family idealization.

Reproductive autonomy recovers a positive vision along with its right to planning so that through new opportunities offered by Medicine today in conjunction with other areas of health so that those who play the role of parents or progenitors, to be more participatory, and decision-making are carried out in much more informed ways, Aware and active in the control, planning and supervision of the best interests of the child in personal development throughout his life talking about the conceived.

A slightly different, although clear and concise example of the implementation and regulation of new practices that are supported by technological advances are for example abortion due to a genetic or congenital malformation, that is, an interruption of pregnancy when noticing through clinical analysis the anomalous development of the product:

"When the product has severe malformations. It exists in 16 states. Applies when serious genetic or congenital alterations or malformations are diagnosed. It is not necessary that the alterations or malformations are incompatible with life outside the womb"

(Ipas Mexico, 2020)

In cases of elective abortion, that is, when the woman chooses or decides to terminate the pregnancy, you can go to public services, particularly in Mexico City, to the Legal Interruption

Clinics in the CDMX, where it is possible to access a safe, legal and generally free procedure or with a small recovery fee, with the support of trained personnel, the right technology and sufficient infrastructure without endangering your life or health.

This example shows the intervention and influence of science and medical advances in a controlled, responsible and autonomous reproduction, which shows and demonstrates that interfering and regularizing these scenarios favors the population in strengthening their rights and the PGD represents a new advance in the path of a broader and more complex family planning object of study to regulate in the Mexican legal system than to date. From the drafting and research of this project this figure is not reflected in the current normative content.

In 1948 sexual and reproductive rights began to be discussed in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights within the framework of the United Nations. Subsequently, in 1966, the International Covenants on Civil and Political Rights and on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights gave more substance to these rights and indicated the duties and responsibilities of States vis-à-vis individuals and defined mechanisms to verify their compliance. From that year, the formal antecedents of the recognition of reproductive rights can be recognized in the following instruments:

"At the UN General Assembly held in 1966 it was stated that: The size of the family should be the free choice of the family"

In 1974, the International Conference on Population and Development in Bucharest adopted the "World Plan of Action for Population", which reaffirmed the right to reproductive decision and expanded it to include couples and individuals.

As such, the choice of having children or not having them was considered a close personal prerogative, so that a human right. In the same way, it was established that the State should have an active role in the protection of this right by offering individuals the means, education and information to make them effective.

In 1984, the World Conference on Population and Development in Mexico reiterated the importance of family idealization as the primary human right of all individuals and couples. As such, progress was made in the concept of "responsibility" in 2 senses:

(1) on the one hand, individuals and couples were urged to exercise their reproductive rights taking into account their own situation and the impact of their choices on the development of their children, the society and society in which they live; and

(2) It was held that, although this right enjoyed general approval, many couples and individuals were in social, economic or cultural conditions that made it impossible to exercise it because they lacked information, education and did not have access to a desirable range of complementary procedures and services.

To this impact, the Conference put 4 relevant news:

1) First, it defined reproductive health as "a general state of physical, mental and social comfort, and not of mere absence of pathologies or ailments, in all points involved with the reproductive

system and its functionalities and processes" which includes "the ability to enjoy a successful and safe sex life and to procreate, and the independence to decide whether or not to do it, at what time and how often";

(2) secondly, it indicated that reproductive health "implies the right of the human being and the lady to obtain information and to have access to safe, effective, affordable and acceptable procedures for idealizing the family nucleus of their choice, as well as other procedures for the regulation of fertility";

3) thirdly, it proclaimed that sexual health follows "the development of life and individual interrelations and not merely guidance and attention to issues of reproduction and sexually transmitted pathologies"; and

4) fourth, established for the first time a criterion of reproductive rights that "encompass certain human rights that are already identified in national laws, in world human rights documents and in other relevant UN documents adopted by consensus" and that "are based on the recognition of the primary right of each of the couples and individuals to independently and responsibly mention the number of children, the spacing and spacing of births and the information and means to do so and the right to attain the highest standard of sexual and reproductive health", which should also include "their right to make choices related to reproduction without discrimination, coercion or ill-treatment, in accordance with the predetermined human rights documents. An easy way to meet the symposium document formatting requirements is to use this document as a template and simply write your text into it.

4. Discussion

Derived to the investigation of what means the preimplantation genetic diagnosis in its purpose as a therapeutic means for third parties, acquiring every child conceived under assisted reproduction through these parameters of the modern era of genetically manipulable medicine is to question the guiding principles of this practice because, from the conventional point of view to the product resulting from the genetic modification which with the process of the reproduction cycle It acquires the character of child supporting us with what mentions the declaration of children with respect to the limits of interference and protection it is necessary to emphasize that indeed, everything conceived is understood by born for the purposes of the higher interest. Since although it is not as such a living product in the first moments of its genetic diagnosis treatment, it is certainly a living organism since fertilization and implantation inviting inside the cervix of the feminine. Here is a prevailing question to try to legislate the law that currently governs the state of Tabasco in civil matters, because the assisted reproduction technique is not expressly or tacitly regulated, there is a legal absence that limits the parameters to conduct and decide in full right a lucrative family planning for medical purposes thus coercing the free development of the personality that the minor has as a fundamental right.

It is incredible the amount of information reported in which it is not questioned from an honest aspect, the ingesting and laceration that is caused by the reason of only having been created as an object for medicine, therefore, its dignity in automatic is violated and interrupted.

5. Conclusions

The state of Tabasco has the fortune of being one of the only states in the Mexican Republic where the practice of assisted reproduction is manifested by the civil law in question but the deficiency found is that there is no agency that can mediate, delimit and resolve the conflict of interests when a minor is medically abused in order to safeguard the integrity of the brother with diseases, thus going against the laws responsible for the protection of children. The claim that medicine has evolved so much to genetically modify a lump of cells is not contradicted, because it is impressive that biogenetics has so far reached the alteration of natural selection.

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